

Principles of Accounting Units 7 & 12

**Introduction to climate-
related financial reporting**

Activity based case study

**Sam Bell, Senior Lecturer, University of
Bristol Business School**

**Accounting
Streams**

Case outline

This case aims to demonstrate links between sustainability reporting and financial accounting at an introductory level by demonstrating how climate-related risks materialise within financial statements under existing accounting standards. Using a range of activities it will help you apply your knowledge of financial accounting to an emerging area of practice and introduce you to climate-related risk.

1. What is climate risk and how does it impact organisations?

The ISSB (International Sustainability Standards Board) define two categories of climate risk that organisations face: physical risks and transition risks.

Climate Risk Type	Explanation
Physical risks	Risks coming from the direct effects of climate change such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Sudden events like storms, floods, wildfires, or droughts which may happen more frequently or severely because of climate change.• Long-term changes such as rising sea levels, higher temperatures, changes in biodiversity and changes in rainfall patterns.
Transition risks	Risks that come from moving towards a low-carbon economy such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• New laws and regulations that affect the organisation such as limits on pollution or bans on products like single-use plastic packaging.• The organisation sets goals/strategies to reach 'net-zero' organisational emissions which require it to change how it operates to reduce greenhouse gas emissions to zero.• Customers demand more eco-friendly products which may require the organisation to change what it makes.• Higher costs in the market for commodities used by the organisation in production such as oil, coal, and gas.

Although for many organisations, climate change risks may have negative impacts, for some organisations climate change may offer opportunities for growth, for example renewable energy providers may benefit from the transition to a low-carbon economy as energy customers seek to source their energy needs from renewable sources.

Activity 1A: Identifying climate risk in the fashion industry

Identify examples of climate risk factors in the fashion industry, populating the table below by reading the article [Why fashion can no longer ignore the climate crisis](#). Whilst the article examines fashion and climate risk in 2024 its approach highlights ongoing climate risks that remain relevant to the industry today.

Climate risk factor	Example found in the article
Drought	
Flooding and monsoons	
Rising sea levels	

High temperatures	
Greenhouse gas (GHG) emission regulations / commitments to achieve net-zero	

2. Why do accountants need to think about climate risk when preparing financial statements?

Many organisations, especially larger, publicly listed companies, produce sustainability reports reporting climate-related information such as carbon emissions, climate risks and organisational strategies to achieve net zero. There are several different sustainability reporting frameworks used by preparers including the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) and ISSB IFRS Sustainability Disclosure Standards.

Users reading climate-related information in an organisation's sustainability report need to be able to understand the financial statement impact of the organisation's climate-related risks and strategies. For many users, climate-related matters will be important (material), and they would expect the financial statements to include this information in their disclosures. This means preparers need to consider climate risk when preparing their financial statements. The IFRS standard setter, IASB, has issued guidance demonstrating how specific climate-related risks and strategies should be reported in an organisation's financial statements.

A significant challenge for preparers is dealing with the uncertainty of climate change such as the likelihood, timing, and extent of the risks. Anderson (2019) notes that even where a company preparing financial statements decides that there is no material impact on the financial statements, investors need adequate explanations in financial statement disclosures to understand why there is no material impact. We will explore how climate-related risks might be reported using a range of scenarios.

3. Scenarios: climate-related risk in financial statements

Property, plant, and equipment

Climate-related risks can cause property, plant, and equipment assets to face reduced useful lives and reduction in value (impairments). This could be due to climate-related factors such as consumers switching to eco-friendly products, changes in legislation and/or company strategy and limitations on asset use caused by physical climate risks such as flooding.

Activity 3A: Urban Link

Urban Link, a bus company operating fast, affordable bus routes nationwide between major cities has published in its sustainability report a commitment to stop using high carbon-emitting diesel vehicles within 5 years. Urban Link will replace their remaining diesel buses with low-carbon emission bio-gas vehicles as they reach the end of their operating life. Currently 40% of the Urban Link bus fleet are low-carbon emission vehicles, the remainder being diesel vehicles. The major cities where Urban Link operates will introduce Low Emission Zones prohibiting high carbon-emitting diesel vehicles over the next 3 years. Urban Link's diesel and bio-gas buses have a total expected useful life of 15 years. Urban Link usually sell their buses to smaller bus operators at the end of their operating life for

around 10% of their original purchase price. The average remaining useful life of Urban Link's diesel bus fleet is 10 years.

Questions

- Identify, giving reasons, the climate-related risk in this scenario.
- Why might the commitment to stop using high carbon-emitting vehicles be considered significant (material) to users of Urban Link's financial statements?
- What adjustments might need to be made to the Urban Link financial statements because of this climate-related risk?

Inventory

Accounting standards require inventories to be valued at the lower of cost and net realizable value. Transition risks such as changes in consumer demand and/or legislation may mean an organisation experiences obsolete or slow-moving items which may need to be sold below cost.

Activity 3B: Thermagas Ltd

Thermagas Ltd manufactures gas boilers for the domestic housing market. For the past 10 years, over 80% of their sales revenue has come from supplying large housebuilding companies with gas boilers for their "new build" housing developments. Thermagas Ltd's remaining revenue comes from gas boiler sales to smaller building companies, who install them when refitting existing homes. Thermagas Ltd hold a large (material) volume of inventory consisting of gas boilers and spare parts for gas boilers in order to quickly fulfil customer orders.

Recently, the government announced new legislation requiring all new build houses to use low-carbon heating systems such as heat pumps from the end of this year. Although gas boilers will no longer be allowed in new builds, they can still be installed in existing homes. Thermagas Ltd is currently developing a heat pump system using its existing production facilities, but it is unlikely to be in production by the end of the year when the legislation takes effect. As a result Thermagas Ltd have seen a dramatic fall in orders placed by their large housebuilding customers. Because inventory levels are so high, the operations director of Thermagas Ltd has been offering gas boilers to customers at drastically discounted prices. The inventories of Thermagas Ltd are currently valued at cost.

Questions

- Identify, giving reasons, the climate-related risk in this scenario.
- What adjustments might need to be made to the Thermagas Ltd financial statements because of this climate-related risk?
- What might happen to Thermagas Ltd as so much of its business is reliant on "new build" customers?

Loans receivable

Climate-related issues can increase the risk that bank loans won't be repaid. For example, events like floods or wildfires, or changes in laws and regulations, can negatively impact borrower income and make it harder for them to pay back their loan to the bank.

Activity 3C: Agribank plc

Agribank plc provide financial support such as loans to agricultural businesses such as coffee farmers. Agribank plc report these loans as financial assets in their financial statements. The area where Agribank's coffee farmer customers are located has been affected over the last 3 years by rising temperatures and increased incidence of the coffee plant disease leaf rust. These events have caused coffee bean production to fall by up to 50% meaning many coffee farmers are facing a significant reduction in their income.

Questions

- Identify, giving reasons, the climate-related risk in this scenario for coffee farmers.
- Why might the risk facing coffee farmers also impact Agribank plc?
- What adjustments might need to be made to Agribank plc's financial statements because of this climate-related risk?

Provisions

Climate-related risk can impact provisions as potential liabilities which the company must settle in the future can arise due to climate-related laws and obligations. There is ongoing debate as to whether expenditure related to a company's decarbonisation strategy (rather than a specific law or contractual obligation) should be treated as a provision (see Accounting Streams Unit 12 Section 12.7 Investment in Net Zero).

Activity 3D: Lithix Group

Lithix Group operate a coal-processing facility which operates with a relatively high level of carbon emissions. Included in the most recent financial statements of Lithix Group is a material provision for decommissioning the facility at the end of its useful life in 2050. By law the company are required to demolish the facility, decontaminate the facility site and plant the site with plants and trees. The coal-processing facility is located in an area impacted by rising temperatures and water-scarcity due to climate change. Lithix Group have just announced their strategy to achieve net-zero carbon emissions by 2040.

Question

How might climate-related risk impact the date of closure of the coal-processing facility? Will the value of the decommissioning provision increase if the coal-processing facility is closed before 2050?

4. Climate-related risks and materiality

When we are thinking about climate-related risks and financial statements, we should consider the two fundamental qualitative characteristics of financial information:

Characteristic	Meaning
Relevance	Information should be useful to the decision-making process. Information should be <i>material</i> ; if it were omitted or misstated, it would potentially influence the decision a user might make.
Faithful representation	Information should represent the true nature of the economic situation or substance of the organisation.

These characteristics mean that not all information about climate-related risk will be reported in the financial statements as it would not be useful for users' decision making and it does not reflect the economic situation of the organisation.

Activity 4A: Materiality company comparison

Two companies have announced net-zero strategies to reduce their emissions over the next 10 years.

Company A manufactures steel. Manufacturing steel uses a lot of energy and produces a high level of greenhouse gas emissions.

Company B is an architectural design business. It is a service-based company where employees design buildings. Service-based organisations usually produce much lower emissions and use far less energy than manufacturing companies.

Question

- *Would you expect the net-zero strategy commitment to have a material impact on financial statements of each of these two companies? Explain your answer.*

5. Double materiality: a wider view of climate risk

Accounting Streams Unit 11 *How should we measure environmental and social costs?* states “Accountants have an ethical duty to ensure that all material social, environmental, and financial consequences are appropriately recognized, valued, and disclosed to internal and external parties. Accountants must not forget their professional responsibility to make businesses aware of and accountable for past, present, and future costs they needlessly inflict on others.”

So far we have considered climate-related risk using a *financial materiality* perspective – which considers the impact that climate-related risk has on the organisation’s financial statements. For example, in Activity 4A for company A the steel manufacturer, you considered the impact a net zero policy has on the entity (e.g., impairment of machinery). This financial materiality approach ignores the impact the organisation, its supply chain and end consumers of its products have on the natural environment. The *double materiality* perspective aims to encompass this wider view of the impact of an entity on the environment, considering not only how physical and transition risks impact the entity but also how the entity’s operations impact the environment. For example, a double materiality perspective could consider how the steel manufacturer’s current operations impact air quality, biodiversity and water scarcity

Activity 5A: Urban Bus revisited

What aspects of the climate-related disclosures might change if a double materiality approach was adopted in relation to the diesel fleet emissions of the Urban Link bus company in Activity 2A?

Summary

Climate-related risks represent a challenge for accountants as they introduce uncertainties impacting accounting judgments and estimates which in turn impact the measurement of assets and liabilities and accounting disclosures.

Climate-related risks are categorised as physical and transition risks. Not all climate-related risks impact the financial statements.

In this case we looked at some examples at an introductory accounting level, where climate-related risks may lead to accountants adjusting asset and liability values and/or including disclosure notes in the financial statements to amplify and explain impact.

- Property, plant and equipment values may reduce as climate-related risks can reduce useful lives and residual values, meaning depreciation is accelerated or cause a fall in value (impairment) as assets become 'stranded' or less economically viable.
- Inventory values may fall, in particular where transition risks cause selling prices to fall, meaning impairments arise as net realisable values fall below cost.
- Institutions, such as banks, who grant loans to their customers can be impacted by climate-related risk, when such risks cause their customers to potentially default on loans. This increases the risk of bad debts, and these increased potential losses will reduce loan asset valuations.
- An organisation's climate commitments and new climate-related legislation can cause new obligations to arise, or accelerate existing obligations, which may increase the size of provisions reported as liabilities.

Those preparing financial statements should account for the material impacts of climate-related risk. Some are critical of this approach and some critics feel applying a financial materiality approach to climate-related reporting does not capture the impact of an organisation's effect on the environment and call for a double materiality approach to be used.

Further questions for reflection

Discuss these statements

Due to the uncertainty and medium to long term nature of climate change, incorporating climate-risk into financial statements makes them less decision useful for most users."

Because most of the climate-related risks cause negative impacts on the financial statements (asset values fall, liabilities increase, expenses increase), we should upwardly revalue organisational assets with an environmental benefit (such as energy efficient technologies) in order to demonstrate neutrality.

Accounting Streams Reading

Recommended pre-reading for this case from Smith, S., Murphy, R. & Rose, J., *Principles of Accounting*. Available at: www.accounting-streams.org

- Unit 7: Unit 7: What is in financial statements? Section 7.4 Judgements and estimates.
- Unit 3: What is the role of data in organisations? Section 3.3 What makes data useful?
- Unit 12: What is carbon accounting? Section 12.2 Why should accountants care about carbon accounting?

References

Anderson N. (2019) IFRS Standards and climate-related disclosures. Available at: <https://www.ifrs.org/content/dam/ifrs/news/2019/november/in-brief-climate-change-nick-anderson.pdf>

Business of Fashion Team, McKinsey & Company (2023) The year ahead: Why fashion can no longer ignore the climate crisis *Business of Fashion* Available at: <https://www.businessoffashion.com/articles/sustainability/the-state-of-fashion-2024-report-climate-crisis-supply-chain-sustainability-environment/>

Conway, E. (2024). What is the role of data in organisations? Unit 3 in Smith, S., Murphy, R. & Rose, J., *Principles of Accounting*. Available at: www.accounting-streams.org

Ellington, F., Ellington P. & Rose J. (2024). What is carbon accounting? Unit 12 in Smith, S., Murphy, R. & Rose, J., *Principles of Accounting*. Available at: www.accounting-streams.org

KPMG (n.d.) The impact of climate risk on the financial statements. Available at: <https://kpmg.com/us/en/articles/2023/impact-climate-risk-financial-statements.html>

Murphy, R. (2024). How do accountants manage risk and uncertainty? Unit 17 in Smith, S., Murphy, R. & Rose, J., *Principles of Accounting*. Available at: www.accounting-streams.org

Rose, J. & Zimmer A. (2024). What is in financial statements? Unit 7 in Smith, S., Murphy, R. & Rose, J., *Principles of Accounting*. Available at: www.accounting-streams.org

Täger M. (2021) 'Double materiality': what is it and why does it matter? *Grantham Research Institute on Climate Change and the Environment* Available at: <https://www.lse.ac.uk/granthaminstitute/news/double-materiality-what-is-it-and-why-does-it-matter/>

Thomson. I. (2024). How should we measure environmental and social costs? Unit 11 in Smith, S., Murphy, R. & Rose, J., *Principles of Accounting*. Available at: www.accounting-streams.org